

Nyctanthes arbor tristis: A Comprehensive review of phytochemistry and pharmacological properties

Dr. Prakash Dabadi, Bhagyashree M^{*}, Dr. A.M. Krupanidhi

Department of pharmacology, Bapuji pharmacy college, Davangere-577004, Karnataka, India.

Corresponding author

Bhagyashree M

Department of Pharmacology, Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere-577004 Karnataka, India

Dr. Prakash Dabadi

Department of Pharmacology, Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere-577004 Karnataka, India

Dr. A M Krupanidhi

Department of Pharmacology, Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere-577004 Karnataka, India

ABSTRACT:

The history of every civilisation has recorded the use of medicinal plants to treat illnesses, interest in aromatic and medicinal plants that has spread throughout the world due to its safe and efficient active ingredients. The medicinal uses of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn belongs to the family Oleaceae, which is widely spread and readily available in nature, are described in the Charaka, Sushruta, and other traditional medical systems. The Ayurvedic medical system uses the *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn, to treat a variety of conditions, including diuresis, liver disorders, spleen enlargement, sciatica, and bitter, stomachic, carminative, hair tonics and including antipyretic, anti-inflammatory, anthelmintic, sedative, laxative and expectorant properties in rheumatoid arthritis. Numerous phytochemicals that can serve as a source of active pharmacological substances are responsible for all of the actions that plants exhibit. The current review provides a thorough compilation of the various phytochemical substances and pharmacological actions that this plant has been shown to exhibit thus far. And *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* is a plant that has a number health benefits and valuable plant for the development of novel therapeutic agents.

Keywords: *Nyctanthes arbor tristis*, pharmacological activity, phytoconstituents, traditional use, antioxidant activity and hepatoprotective activity.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Nyctanthes arbor-tristis Linn. is a significant medicinal plant that has been used for a variety of illness since ancient times. Many elements of this plant have been used as traditional and indigenous remedies. *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* can treat a variety of ailments and exhibits a wide range of pharmacological activities [1]. It is often grown as an ornamental in Indian gardens because to its very fragrant flowers [2]. The genus name "Nyctanthes" comes from the Greek words "Nykhta," which means night, and "anther," which means flower. There are around 600 species of tiny vines and trees in the genus Night Jasmine, which is a member of the Oleaceae family of plants [3].

It is widespread across India, but mostly in the dry and semi-arid regions of Northwestern India, the lower Western Himalayan range, and the Upper Gangetic Plain. The sub-Himalayan area stretches from the Chenab to Nepal, Chhota Nagpur, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, and south to the Godavari. The seeds and flowers of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* L. have CNS depressing qualities, mild antispasmodic action, and antipyretic and anti-inflammatory qualities. This plant has also been demonstrated to possess antimalarial, antiallergic, amoebicidal, and anthelmintic qualities [4].

Natural bioactive compounds, which could also result in the creation of novel therapeutic medicines. A significant class of drugs used to cure ailments, plant-based pharmaceuticals have become more and more popular in the last ten years. Herbs are resurfacing, and a global herbal "renaissance" is occurring. The one that, in contrast to synthetics, which are regarded as dangerous for both humans and the environment, herbal products. Now represent safety. In order to cure intestinal worms, malaria, intractable sciatica, and arthritis, Ayurvedic physicians commonly use the leaf decoction as a laxative, cholagogue, and tonic [5].

Buddhist monks were the first to use the orange heart to dye cotton and silk, since the flower was used to decorate their orange robes. One of the five wish-granting trees of Devaloka in Hindu mythology is the Parijata⁵. Another name for *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* is the "tree of sorrow," because its blossoms lose their brilliance during the day [6].

Throughout history, people have made beneficial use of its leaves, stalks, roots, flowers, fruits, and seeds. The leaves of this plant have been used by Ayurvedic practitioners to cure a wide range of illnesses, such as sciatica, joint pain, coughing, chronic fever, arthritis, parasitic worms, rheumatism, constipation, etc [7].

2. PLANT PROFILE:

2.1. Taxonomical Classification [3,6,8&9]

Kingdom	: Plantae
Division	: Magnoliophyta
Class	: Magnoliopsida
Order	: Lamiales
Family	: Oleaceae
Genus	: Nyctanthes
Species	: <i>N. arbor-tristis</i>

2.2. vernacular names: [3,9-12]

English : Tree of Sorrow, Night Jasmine, Coral Jasmine

Kannada : Parijatha.

Hindi : Harsingar.

Marathi : Parijathak.

Tamil : Pavalamalli

Telugu : Pagadamalle

Sanskrit : Parijatha.

Siddha : Pavazha mattigai.

Ayurvedic : Paarijaata, Shephaali, Shephaalika, Mandaara.

Punjabi : Harsinghar

Bengali : Harsinghar, Sephalika, Seoli, Sheoli.

2.3. Geographical distribution:

Native to India, *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn can be found all over the sub-Himalayan region, extending south to the Godavari. It is also widely distributed in tropical and sub-tropical South East Asia, the Indo-Pak peninsula, and Bangladesh. It is found in the Terai regions, Ceylon, and Burma and grows in the Indo-Malayan region.¹⁰ Its geographical range includes Assam, Burma, Bengal, Central India, which includes Rajasthan and Madhya Pradesh, as well as various locations throughout the world, from northern Pakistan and southern Nepal to northern India and southeast to Thailand [12].

2.4. phytochemical-constituents: [7,13-15]

Plant parts	Phyto-constituents
Bark	Alkaloids, Glycosides [13].
Flowers	D-Mannitol, Tannin, Glucose, Carotenoid, Essential Oil, Nyctanthin, Glycosides, α -crocetin (or crocin-3), β -monogentiobioside, β -monogentiobioside- β -D, β -digentiobioside. Crocetin, Crocin [15], Apigenin, Anthocyanin, Kaemferol, Quercetin, Rengylone, Stigmasterol, Rengyolone, 2-Phenylethyl- β -D-glucopyranoside, n-Tetradecyl β -D-glucopyranoside [14].
Leaves	Ascorbic Acid, Benzoic Acid, Carotene, D-Mannitol, Flavanol Glycosides, Astragaline, Friedeline, Fructose, Glucose, Iridoid Glycosides, Lupeol, Mannitol, Methyl Salicylate, Nicotiflorin, Nyctanthic Acid, Oleanolic Acid, Tannic Acid, β -Sitosterole, Calceolarioside A, Arborside A, Arborside B, Betulinic acid [15].

Seeds	3-4 Secotriterpene Acid, Arbotristoside A, B, D&E, Glycerides of Linoleic Oleic, Lignoceric, Myristic Acids, Nyctanthic Acid, Palmitic [15], Stearic, Iridoid glucosides, a Pale-Yellow Brown Oil (15%) [16].
Stem	Glycoside – naringenin – 4'-O-B-glucapyranosyl-cc-xylopyranoside, β -Sitosterole and B-sitosterol, Lignoceric acid, Pelargonic acid, Friedel-1-ene-3-one, 1-Triacontanol [14].
Flower oil	Anisaldehyde, Phenyl acetaldehyde, p-cymene, 1-deconol, 1- hexanol methyl heptanone, α -pinene [15].
Roots	Alkaloids, tannins and glucosides [13].

Fig 1: *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* flower

Morphological characteristics:

The average height of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* is between 15 and 25 meters, with a spread of about 30 meters [6].

- **LEAVES:** The simple, dissimilarly orientated leaves, The entire edge of it is covered in reticulated venation. Simple, petiolate, and exstipulate leaves are also present. Oval in shape, the lamina has an acute or acuminate apex, a whole, slightly undulating edge, especially close to the base, and a dark green top surface with dotted glands [16].
- **FLOWERS:** Clearly visible at the tips of branches are clusters of two to seven flowers. They are small and bright, with a white corolla and an orange center. Individual blooms open at nightfall and fall off at sunrise [17].
- **FRUITS:** The fruits have a diameter of 2 cm, are bilobate, brown, laterally compressed, and resemble a heart or spherical capsule with one seed in each lobe.
- **SEED:** Compacted seeds, which have one seed per cell, are highly vascularized, have a broad, transparent cell layer on the outside, and a thick testa.

- BARK: *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* can grow up to 10 m (33 cm) tall, with quadrangular branches, dark grey or brown bark that is solid and rough, and a dip in the bark surface caused by circular flakes scaling off the bark. The inner bark is creamy white, mushy, and collapsed, with no clearly apparent collapsed phloem zone.
- ROOTS: The plant's roots include glucosides, tannins, and alkaloids. It is possible to isolate β Sitosterol and oleanolic acid [10].

Traditional use of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* Linn

- Leaf juice is used as a laxative, tonic, diuretic, digestive aid, and antidote to reptile venom. Additionally, splenic hypertrophy is treated using leaves. Traditional uses for the powdered stem bark include treating malaria, rheumatism, and expectoration [15].
- For many years, *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* has been used to treat a variety of illnesses, such as rheumatism, persistent sciatica, malaria, bronchitis, wound healing, skin issues, stomachic, astringent, menstrual, biliary, liver, and chronic fever, according to scientific literature [18].
- The usage of orange hearts to dye silk and cotton dates back to Buddhist monks, who utilized this flower to give their orange robes its color [19].
- Its flowers have ophthalmic uses. The floral juice is applied as a hair tonic to stop baldness and graying of the hair [19].
- The woods serve as a batten base for the roofs grass covering or tiling. Baskets are made from of young branches. Its leaves can be used to polish wood and ivory, and its bark can be utilized as a tanning substance [20].
- barks to prevent diarrhea and dysentery [21]. Historically, the powdered stem bark was used to treat bronchitis and snakebite.
- The seeds are used to treat alopecia and as anthelmintics. In addition to being an expectorant and antibilious, it also helps with bilious fevers. The powdered seeds are used to treat skin conditions, piles, and scurvy affections [22].
- *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* is typically used as a traditional medicine in Indonesia to treat asthma, cough, discomfort, irregular menstruation, fever, and hemorrhoids [14].

3. PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTION:

3.1. WOUND HEALING ACTIVITY

Rats were given a 2% w/w ointment of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* methanolic extract for 16 days, with observations made every 4 days. This is the time when the wound heals completely. Therefore, it can be said that the plant extract, at a dose of 300 mg/kg b.w, may be an effective way to help both wounds heal [23].

3.2. HEPATOPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY

Nyctanthes arbor-tristis leaves protects the liver from the harmful effects of carbon tetra chloride. At a dose of 200 mg/kg body weight, the results showed that both the alcoholic and aqueous extracts demonstrated considerable hepatoprotective efficacy by lowering the increased levels of biochemical markers. Histopathological analyses of liver samples that demonstrated hepatocyte regeneration by the extracts hence shows a significant hepatoprotective activity [24].

3.3. ANTI BACTERIAL ACTIVITY

Using the agar disc diffusion method, ten medically significant bacterial strains—including *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas species.*, *Staphylococcus epidermis*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus species*, and *Bacillus subtilis*—were used *in vitro* antibacterial investigations on the ethanolic leaf extracts. The four extract concentrations that were administered to the bacterial strains were

50 mg/ml, 100 mg/ml, 200 mg/ml, and 300 mg/ml solvent. The findings of our antibacterial tests demonstrated that the extract showed good inhibitory action against all the tested pathogens compared with traditional antibiotics like streptomycin and penicillin. It was discovered that the inhibitory activity was dosage dependant [25].

3.4. ANTI DIABETIC ACTIVITY

Streptozotocin (55 mg/kg, i.p.) was used to induce diabetes in the animals. After the diabetes level was shown to be greater than 300 mg/dl, the rats were given chloroform extract from *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaves and flowers (50, 100, and 200 mg/kg) for 27 days. When compared to control (diabetic patients treated with vehicles), the extract considerably ($P < 0.05$, $P < 0.01$, $P < 0.001$) decreased serum glucose levels in treated rats. The chloroform extract of the leaves and flowers had antidiabetic effects that were similar to those of glibeclamide taken orally at a dose of 10 mg/kg (positive control). However, after 27 days of treatment, the flower extract showed more significance. This study demonstrates that *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* has a stronger antidiabetic effect on its flowers than on its leaves [26].

3.5. ANTICANCER ACTIVITY:

To assess the antiproliferative properties of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* floral extracts. In vitro tests were used to examine the 95% ethanol-extracted shade-dried flowers. Using various human cancer cell lines, the MTT test was used to measure the antiproliferative activity. When tested against the Colo 205 cell line, the lowest IC₅₀ value was $24.56 \pm 6.63 \mu\text{g/mL}$. There were antiproliferative effects of the extract [27].

3.6. ANTI ALLERGIC ACTIVITY:

Significant protection against the development of suffocation was provided by pretreating the guinea pigs exposed to histamine aerosol with a water-soluble part of the alcoholic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* linn leaves. According to reports, arbortristosides A and C have anti-allergic properties [28].

3.7. ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:

Butanol, ethyl acetate, pet ether, and aqueous fractions were separated from the dried leaves of the alcoholic extract *Nyctanthes arbor tristis*. In vitro evaluation of free radical scavenging was conducted using the diphenyl-picryl hydrazyl (DPPH) test. Ascorbic acid and BHT, two standards and plant extracts, have a decreasing scavenging action on the DPPH radical in the following order: BHT, Butanol, Ethyl Acetate, and Pet Ether were found to be 93.88% at a concentration of 10 μg , 97.42%, 95.22%, 84.63%, and 82.04% at a concentration of 100 μg , respectively, whereas ascorbic acid was found to be 93.88%. Various *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* leaf extracts shown concentration-dependent free radical scavenging activities in the current investigation [29].

3.8. ANTIGENOTOXIC ACTIVITY:

Genotoxicity is defined as the damage that chemicals cause to cells' genetic information. Using the Ames test with the standard Salmonella assay, the ethanolic extract of the NAT flower and its constituent, crocin, were evaluated for genotoxic activity. The extract and crocin were nongenotoxic at doses of 125–2,000 μg with and without metabolic activation. The lack of genotoxicity

data of other *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* extracts and their phytoconstituent encourages further studies to confirm the safety of complementary medicine [30].

3.9. ANTI MALARIAL ACTIVITY:

patients with malaria were treated with fresh five leaves of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* administered orally for 7-10 days. The reduction of symptoms and indicators of malaria and the features of Visham jwara were rated basally and daily. Ninety-two (76.7%) of the 120 patients exhibited full clinical and parasite recovery in just seven days. After ten days, the remaining twenty patients who were receiving the same treatment were cured. Standard antimalarial treatment was administered to those patients who did not respond clinically or by parasitic clearance [31].

3.10. ANTI INFLAMMATORY AND ANALGESIC ACTIVITY:

Methanol was used to extract the stem bark of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn. in order to assess its analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties. Using morphine sulphate as the reference medication at a dose of 5 mg/kg of body weight, the analgesic activity was assessed on Wistar albino rats using the hot plate method, tail flick assay, and tail immersion method. The data were presented as the mean increase in latency following drug administration \pm SEM. Carrageenan-induced rat paw oedema was used to measure the anti-inflammatory action. Diclofenac sodium, a common medication, was administered at a dose of 100 mg/kg of body weight. The results were expressed as the mean increase in paw volume \pm SEM. Two dosages of stem bark extract were administered: 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg of body weight. According to the findings, *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn. had potent analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities [32].

3.11. ANTI TUSSIVE ACTIVITY:

A cough is also an indication of body abnormalities or the existence of certain diseases. The carbohydrate polymer (CP) extracted from the aqueous extract of NAT leaves decreased coughs in guinea pigs caused by citric acid by up to 66.5% at a dose of CP 50 mg/kg. The activity was marginally lower than the codeine phosphate-induced activity (62.1%). Furthermore, the results of in vivo tests demonstrated that CP had a noteworthy impact when given [33]

3.12. ANXIETY ACTIVITY:

Rats given ethanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* exhibited signs of anxiolysis, as evidenced by a marked increase in the amount of time spent in open arms, the number of head dips on the elevated plus maze, and the number of entries in open arms. Compared to control rats, the rats given NAT 500 mg/kg spent noticeably more time interacting with others [34].

3.13. ANTI VIRAL ACTIVITY:

In vivo ethanolic extract and n-butanol fraction at daily doses of 125 mg/kg weight protected EMCV infected mice against SFV by 40 and 60%, respectively. Based on the aforementioned results, it was determined that plants have a significant antiviral activity against SFV. The ethanolic extract, n-butanol fractions, and two pure compounds, arbortristoside C, isolated from the *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* have pronounced inhibitory activity against encephalomyocarditis virus (EMCV) and Semliki forest virus (SFV) [35].

3.14. ANTI TRYPANOSOMAL ACTIVITY:

A crude 50% ethanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* leaves was tested for its antitrypanosomal potential both in vitro and in vivo. The extract demonstrated trypanocidal activity at the highest concentration tested (1000 µg/ml), and in vivo studies showed that it had antitrypanosomal effects at intraperitoneal doses of 300 and 1000 mg/kg and significantly extended the survival period of the mice infected with *Trypanosoma evansi* [36].

3.15. CNS DEPRESSANTS ACTIVITY:

The ethanol extract of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* L. flowers, seeds, leaves, and barks (600 mg/kg) may have a CNS depressive effect and prolong pentobarbitone-induced sleep duration because it raises 5-hydroxytryptamine levels in the brain and decreases dopamine [37].

3.16. ANTI IMMUNOSTIMULANT ACTIVITY:

The anti-immunosuppressive activity of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* leaves aqueous extract in malathion-exposed immunosuppressed mice. The immune restorative potential of HL (aq) was assessed by examining a number of immunological parameters (humoral, cell mediated immune, immunocyte numbers, and phagocyte functions) in mice treated with HL (aq) or not treated with malathion. The findings showed that the immunological parameters that were suppressed by malathion either returned to normal when treated with HL (aq) extract [38].

3.17. ULCEROGENIC ACTIVITY:

The effects of 6-HL and AT on alcohol-induced stomach ulcers were investigated in a rat model. While the reference drug sucralfate only provided 65.67% protection against ethanol-induced ulcers, the ethanol extract of *Nyctanthes arbour tristis*, which contains the chemicals AT and 6HL, showed notable anti-ulcer benefits, providing 72.41% and 80.67% protection, respectively [39].

3.18. ANTI HYPERLIPIDEMIC ACTIVITY:

To evaluate the hypolipidemic effects of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* floral aqueous formulations, male adult mice were given the flower's aqueous extracts orally as a dose-dependent approach in vivo. The hypolipidemic effects of oral ingestion were shown to be both safe and encouraging [40].

3.19. ANTI ARTHRITIC ACTIVITY

Nyctanthes arbor tristis leaves and fruits extract reduced pro inflammatory cytokines and increased antiinflammatory cytokines and increased antiinflammatory cytokines in the joint homogenate of arthritic mice, ultimately resulting in moderate control over the progression of arthritis. this suggests that balance between pro inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokine is required to control the progression of arthritis and the extract from the leaves and fruits has anti arthritic properties [41].

3.20. SEDATIVE ACTIVITY

The sedative effects of a hot infusion of the flowers were tested on rats. Male rats showed dose-dependent conscious sedative activity in this test, but female rats showed no change. strength and muscle coordination at these dosages. Even at the highest dosage, neither blood glucose levels nor *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* were impacted. However, there was a significant reduction in the small intestine's capacity to absorb glucose. The sedation was partially caused by the extract's membrane-stabilizing and antioxidant qualities [42].

3.21. ANTISPASMODIC ACTIVITY AND ANTIHELMENTIC ACTIVITY:

Using earthworms (*Pheretima posthuma*), the ethanolic extracts of different sections of *Nyctanthes arbour tristis* Linn. were examined for anthelmintic activity using the procedure described by Kailashraj and Kurup. Compared to piperazine citrate, the extracts' antispasmodic efficacy was lower. While its seeds and blooms had a fatal effect on the worms, the extracts were discovered to have concentration-dependent paralytic activity. It was also observed that the addition of atropine intensified the ethanolic extracts' paralytic and fatal effects. This suggests that the extracts' anthelmintic impact results from their ability to limit motility by relaxing and reducing sensitivity to acetylcholine's contractile action [43].

3.22. ANTI MICROBIAL AND ANTI FUNGAL

Nyctanthes arbour tristis linn stem bark chloroform, petroleum ether, and ethanolic extract were used as standard medications, along with ciprofloxacin and flucanazole. demonstrated antibacterial and antifungal activity in vitro against *Aspergillus niger*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *E. coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Micrococcus luteus*, and *Candida albicans* using the cup plate method [44].

3.23. ANTI PYRETIC ACTIVITY

The aqueous soluble fraction of the ethanolic extract of the leaves showed significant aspirin-like antinociceptive activity by preventing albino mice from writhing when exposed to acetic acid; however, the extract did not produce morphine-like analgesia, as shown by the mouse tail-clip and rat tail flick methods; it also showed antipyretic activity against brewer's yeast-induced pyrexias in rats, and when administered orally for six days in a row, it resulted dose-dependent gastric ulcers in rats[45].

4. CONCLUSION

A important medicinal plant, *Nyctanthes arbour tristis* is a unique source of beneficial metabolites, including Alkaloids, phytosterols, phenolics, tannins, flavonoids, glycoside and tannins. These treatments have a lower level of toxicity than other pharmaceuticals. Although, the conclusion of this review is fully convenient from the use of these plants as immunomodulators and commencing therapeutic agents, during COVID -19, as well as to promote immunity. The chemical constituents of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* may represent a novel and natural source for the pharmaceutical, food, and fragrance sectors. According to our research review, *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* has biologically significant activity that can successfully protect people against a range of illnesses.

Since the plant is readily available and no special conditions are needed to grow and harvest it, it may be a better option to treat the ailments. It has a wide range of pharmacological actions that may be therapeutically beneficial for the population's overall

health and wellness, necessitating further clinical research. This review provides information about the significance of *Parijata*. *Nyctanthes arbour tristis* is possibly a "treasure house" of therapeutic components that effectively cures a wide range of diseases in an astounding way.

Author contribution

Bhagyashree M conceptualized, investigated, collected data, and wrote the original draft. Prakash Dabadi reviewed and edited the manuscript. A. M. Krupanidhi supervised the manuscript. All authors reviewed and finalized the manuscript for submission.

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The authors declare no conflict of interest, financial or personal, that could have influenced the work presented in this paper.

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